

EFFECT OF RELATIVE DENSITY ON SHOCK WAVE SPEED OF CELLULAR MATERIAL UNDER DYNAMIC IMPACT

Shilong Wang¹, Yuanyuan Ding¹, Changfeng Wang², Zhijun Zheng^{1*}, Jilin Yu¹

¹ CAS Key Laboratory of Mechanical Behavior and Design of Materials,
University of Science and Technology of China, Hefei, Anhui 230026, PR China

² Continuous Extrusion Research Center, Dalian Jiaotong University,
Dalian, Liaoning 116028, PR China

* Corresponding author. Email: zjzheng@ustc.edu.cn (Z.J. Zheng)

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ABSTRACT

Cellular material under high-velocity impact has one typical deformation feature of layer-wise collapse, which is usually characterized by a shock wave. The shock wave speed is strongly dependent on the impact velocity, but it is still unclear that how the cell morphology and material parameters affect the values of shock wave speed. This study is focused on understanding the influence of relative density on the shock wave speed of closed-cell metallic foam under high constant-velocity impact. Closed-cell foam specimens with different relative densities are constructed with a three-dimensional Voronoi technique and their dynamic impact responses are investigated by using the finite element method. The velocity field of a whole specimen at a particular time is obtained from the cell-based finite element model and the one-dimensional velocity distribution along the impact direction is then determined. It is evident that there is a rapid change of particle velocity in the one-dimensional velocity distribution, which corresponds to the location of the shock front. The shock wave speed is thus determined by calculating the time derivative of the shock-front location. Results show that the shock wave speed has a nearly linear relation with the impact velocity at a particular relative density of foam. It is also found that at a particular impact velocity, the shock wave speed increases with the increase of the relative density of foam in a certain extent. An expression of the shock wave speed with respect to the impact velocity and the relative density of foam are obtained. This expression is further compared with that predicted by a shock model based on a rate-independent, rigid-plastic hardening idealization with two material parameters, namely the initial crush stress and the strain hardening parameter, whose values vary with the relative density of foam.

1 INTRODUCTION

Cellular materials, such as honeycombs and metal foams, have been widely used as energy absorption and anti-blast materials [1] for their ability to have a long collapse plateau with a nearly unchanged load [2]. Understanding the effect of material parameters, such as relative density and cell morphology, on their mechanical properties especially under dynamic impact may be helpful to improve the design of cellular structures.

Under high-velocity impact cellular materials deform in the manner of a layer-by-layer collapse of cells. This localized deformation with the sequential collapse of cells could be characterized as a shock wave [3]. Thus, some continuum-based shock models have been proposed to predict the dynamic response of cellular materials under dynamic impact. A one-dimensional shock model, based on a rate-independent, rigid-perfectly plastic-locking (R-P-P-L) idealization, was first proposed by Reid and Peng [4] to explain the strength enhancement of wood under impact loading. The R-PP-L shock model was further applied to analyze other cellular materials and present a first-order approximation of the dynamic behavior [5]. With the deepening research of cellular materials, a series of much accurate shock models have been developed [6-11].

Such simple shock models could approximately describe the dynamic behavior of cellular material [12], but they do not have the ability to explore the dynamic stress-strain behavior. Experimental tests and numerical simulations have been demonstrated to understand the features of the shock wave propagation and to explore the rate-sensitivity mechanisms of cellular materials. Zou et al. [13] investigated the character of the crushing front in hexagonal-cell honeycombs through the distribution of the sectional velocity and strain. Liao et al. [14] developed a local strain field method to study the features of localized deformation and to calculate the shock wave velocity for 2D cellular materials under different impact velocities. Barnes et al. [15] and Gaitanaros et al. [16] carried out experimental and numerical tests on open-cell aluminum foams under direct and stationary impact and obtained a linear relationship between the shock wave speed V_s and the impact velocity V , written as

$$V_s = kV + c_2, \quad (1)$$

where k and c_2 are fitting parameters. Zheng et al. [9] investigated the dynamic behavior of closed-cell foam by using a 3D cellular model, proposed a dynamic stress-strain relation for cellular materials and applied it to develop a rate-dependent, rigid-plastic hardening (D-R-PH) shock model, which could directly give a very simple relation of the shock wave speed

$$V_s = v + c_1, \quad (2)$$

where c_1 is a material parameter and v the instantaneous impact velocity. These findings strengthen the understanding of the features of the shock wave propagation through cellular material under dynamic crushing, but it is still unclear that how the material parameters (e.g. the relative density) affect the values of shock wave speed.

This paper aims to investigate the effect of relative density on the shock wave speed of closed-cell foams under constant-velocity impact. The velocity field distribution is used to characterize the feature of shock front propagation and to calculate the shock wave speed. A quantitative relation of shock wave speed with respect to the impact velocity and the relative density is presented and the hardening behavior of cellular materials under quasi-static and dynamic loading is investigated.

2 NUMERICAL SIMULATION METHOD

2.1 Finite element models

Voronoi technique [17] is employed to construct the geometric model of closed-cell foams. For details, one can refer to the paper by Zheng et al. [9]. A 3D Voronoi structure is generated in a volume

of $20 \times 20 \times 30 \text{ mm}^3$ with 600 nuclei and its degree of cell irregularity [18] is set to be 0.4. The average cell size, d_0 , is about 3.3 mm. The thickness of cell walls in a specimen is identical. The density of Voronoi structures, ρ_0 , is changed by varying the cell-wall thickness. The relative density of the model is expressed as $\rho = \rho_0/\rho_s$, where ρ_s is the density of cell-wall material.

The finite element code ABAQUS/Explicit [19] is used to perform the numerical simulations. The cell-wall material is assumed to be elastic-perfectly plastic with the density $\rho_s = 2700 \text{ kg/m}^3$, the Young's modulus $E = 69 \text{ GPa}$, the Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0.3$ and the yield stress $\sigma_{ys} = 170 \text{ MPa}$. The cell walls of the model are meshed with shell elements of types S3R and S4R. The element size is controlled to be $\sim 0.3 \text{ mm}$ according to the convergence analysis of element size. To save the computational time, shell elements of type S3R with a sharp angle are eliminated. A finite element model of closed-cell foam is shown in Fig. 1a.

Figure 1: A finite element model of closed-cell foam (a) and its loading schematic diagram (b).

2.2 Loading scheme and quasi-static response

Uniaxial constant-velocity compression is considered as the loading scheme in this study. The specimen is placed between two rigid plates: one is fully constrained and the other moves at a constant velocity along the longitudinal direction of the specimen, as shown in Fig. 1b. A linear multi-point constraint was applied to the surfaces at the loading direction to avoid the rollover of the specimen under high velocity impact. The general contact is applied to the overall finite model to satisfy the complex contact behavior among the cell walls with the friction coefficient 0.02.

The quasi-static nominal stress-strain relation of a specimen is obtained from the compression test at a relatively low velocity ($V = 10 \text{ m/s}$). The nominal stress is defined as the reaction force on the loading plate divided by the initial cross-sectional area of the specimen. The nominal strain is the ratio of the reduction in length of the specimen to its initial length. These quasi-static stress-strain curves consist of three typical stages: a linear-elastic stage, a long plastic plateau stage and a rapid compaction stage, see Fig. 2a. The rate-independent, rigid-plastic hardening (R-PH) idealization [9] is used to characterize the plastic deformation and hardening behavior of the cellular structures, written as

$$\sigma(\varepsilon) = \sigma_0 + \frac{C\varepsilon}{(1-\varepsilon)^2}, \quad (3)$$

where σ_0 is the initial crushing stress and C the strain hardening parameter of the cellular material.

Figure 2: (a) Quasi-static nominal stress–strain curves of cellular materials and the R-PH idealization; (b) Variations of parameters σ_0 and C with the relative density of cellular materials.

The influence of relative density on the two parameters σ_0 and C in the R-PH model is investigated by fitting the quasi-static nominal stress-strain curve for a range of relative densities. The results indicate that both of them increase with the increase of relative density in power-law forms, as shown in Fig. 2b, and can be written as

$$\begin{cases} \sigma_0 / \sigma_{ys} = 0.885 \rho^{1.37} \\ C / \sigma_{ys} = 0.115 \rho^{1.50} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Then, Eq. (3) can be rewritten as

$$\frac{\sigma(\varepsilon)}{\sigma_{ys}} = 0.885 \rho^{1.37} + 0.115 \rho^{1.50} \frac{\varepsilon}{(1-\varepsilon)^2}. \quad (5)$$

The above expression shows that the quasi-static response of cellular material is strongly dependent on the relative density. The model could well characterize the quasi-static stress-strain relations of cellular materials in the plastic plateau stage and compaction stage.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 The velocity field and shock wave speed

The highly localized shock-like deformation is a typical deformation feature in cellular materials under dynamic crushing, which is classified as the Shock Mode [20]. The shock wave, which is used to characterize the layer-wise collapse [3], propagates from the loading end towards the supporting end in cellular materials under dynamic impact. The local velocity field was introduced to investigate the relation between the shock wave speed and the impact velocity, which quantitatively describes the behavior of shock wave propagation.

From the numerical results, the one-dimensional velocity distribution could be obtained by averaging the velocity component along the loading direction at every Lagrangian location, as shown

in Fig. 3a. The velocity distribution shows that the velocity along the impact direction drops rapidly at a specific location, which is considered as the location of the shock front. The specimen is divided into three parts: the highly compacted region behind the shock front, the small strain region ahead of the shock front and the rapid change region with a width of about one cell size around the shock front, as done in 2D cellular materials under constant-velocity impact [14]. Theoretically, the physical quantities (such as stress, strain and velocity) across the shock front are discontinuities and there exists a first-order singular surface of these physical quantities. This indicates that the change of those physical quantities happen suddenly across the shock front. However, the shock front always has a finite width for the response of materials practically [13-14], which corresponds to the slope, whose value varies with the strength of current shock wave, on the velocity distribution.

Figure 3: (a) The velocity distribution in the specimen with a relative density of 0.1 under constant-velocity impact of 200 m/s; (b) The velocity gradient and the shock front location at 0.05 ms.

The accurate location of the shock front at a specific time is determined from the maximum absolute value of velocity gradient. Fig. 3b shows a velocity distribution and the corresponding gradient distribution at a certain time. The velocity gradient has a region of rapid change with the width of about one cell size, where the transition of the cross-sectional state happens [10]. When the shock front propagates to a specific position, this local velocity jumps to a high level with the value equals to the impact velocity and the cells at this position are compacted tightly. This event occurs in a finite time, which is equivalent to the time interval that the shock front travels a distance of about one-cell-size [21], as the change of material state is not instantaneous. The extreme point on the velocity gradient curve is defined as the Lagrangian location of shock front at the corresponding time. Fig. 4 shows the Lagrangian location of the shock front versus time for different constant impact velocities. It exhibits a nearly linear relation of the shock front over time during crushing. The shock wave speed is determined by fitting the data linearly. The result shows that the shock wave steadily propagates through the cellular material under constant-velocity impact and the shock wave speed increases with the increase of impact velocity.

The relationship between the shock wave speed and the impact velocity for different relative densities is shown in Fig. 5a. It is found that the shock wave speed increases linearly with the increase of impact velocity and it also increases with the increase of relative density. By fitting the data with the empirical relation in Eq. (1), the variation of the coefficient k with the relative density is obtained,

as shown in Fig. 5b. The coefficient k has an approximated value of 1 and the maximum relative error is less than 5%. Barnes et al. [15] and Gaitanaros et al. [16] also obtained such linear relation between the shock wave speed and the impact velocity with the coefficient $k = 0.9797$ experimentally and 0.996 numerically for open-cell foams with relative density of ~ 0.08 . As the coefficient k is nearly independent of the relative density of cellular material, its value could be taken as 1 for convenience. Thus, Eq. (1) may be simplified into Eq. (2), which further indicates the reliability of the D-P-RH model for cellular materials.

Figure 4: The Lagrangian location of shock front versus time.

From Fig. 3a, it is found that the velocity ahead of the shock front is not zero. It means that the velocity jump across the shock front is not equal to the impact velocity. This is a difference between the constant-velocity impact scenario and the direct impact scenario. Zou et al. [13] pointed out that the cross-section ahead of the shock front has a previous low velocity to act as the precursor of the incoming shock wave in honeycomb. The local strain field distribution of the 2D cellular structures under constant-velocity impact indicates the plastic collapse also occurs at the supporting end once the crushing event happens [14], which results in the motion of the region ahead of the shock front. Nevertheless, the effect of the particle velocity ahead of the shock front was not considered under constant-velocity impact when studying the relation between the shock wave speed and the impact velocity in the literature [15-16].

(a)

(b)

Figure 5: (a) Variations of the shock wave speed with the impact velocity under different relative densities; (b) Variations of the coefficient k with different relative densities.

The cell-based numerical simulations have revealed that the dynamic densification strain is larger than that the quasi-static one [9] and a dynamic material model, the D-P-RH idealization [9], was proposed to describe the hardening behavior of cellular materials. It has a similar form to Eq. (3), given by

$$\sigma(\varepsilon) = \sigma_0^d + \frac{D\varepsilon}{(1-\varepsilon)^2}, \quad (6)$$

where D and σ_0^d are the dynamic hardening parameter and the dynamic initial crushing stress, respectively. The conservations of mass and momentum across the shock front [22] are expressed as:

$$[v] = V_s[\varepsilon], \quad (7)$$

and

$$[\sigma] = \rho_0 V_s [v], \quad (8)$$

where the sign $[]$ represents the jump across the shock front. Combining Eq. (7) and Eq. (8), we have

$$[\sigma] = \frac{\rho_0 [v]^2}{[\varepsilon]}. \quad (9)$$

The particle velocity just ahead of the shock front could be ignored in the present loading scenario. However, the portion ahead of the shock front moves as a whole, except for the plastic collapse portion near the supporting end. Thus, the strain just ahead of the shock front could be ignored. Combining Eq. (6) and Eq. (9) with $[\sigma] = \sigma - \sigma_0^d$ and $[\varepsilon] = \varepsilon - 0$ gives the strain behind the shock front as

$$\varepsilon = \frac{[v]}{c + [v]}, \quad (10)$$

where $[v] = V_B - V_A$ and $c = \sqrt{D/\rho_0}$ with V_B and V_A being the particle velocities behind and ahead of the shock front, respectively. Then, the relation between the shock wave speed V_s and $[v]$ could be obtained by eliminating the strain term in Eq. (7) and Eq. (10), written as

$$V_s = [v] + c. \quad (11)$$

It indicates that the shock wave speed should be linearly related to the velocity jump across the shock front but not to the impact velocity, which is an amendment to Eq. (2).

3.2 The velocity ahead of the shock front

There is a fact that the velocity ahead of the shock front during crushing is non-zero, as shown in Fig. 3. The shock front travels along the loading direction of the cellular material as a planar wave and the velocity ahead of the shock front has a slight graded distribution over the Lagrangian location. The material state at a specific location changes from a pre-existing non-zero value to the final velocity when the shock front goes through. Thus, the region ahead of shock front but away from the supporting end could be served as a precursor of the incoming shock wave during crushing. In this region, the shortened length of the specimen leads to a steep velocity distribution as the shock front propagates. The behavior of the velocity transition in this region is probably explained as the dispersion of the elastic bending wave in cell walls [13].

Figure 6: The velocity ahead of the shock front versus dimensionless time.

Since the portion of the specimen ahead of shock front is not stationary, it is necessary to determine the velocity ahead of the shock front, which may affect the shock wave speed according to Eq. (11). The region around the Lagrangian location $\Phi(t)$ ranging from $\Phi(t) + d_0/2$ to $\Phi(t) + 3d_0/2$ is defined as the effective length on the specimen to calculate the velocity ahead of shock front at time t , as depicted in Fig. 3b. By averaging the cross-sectional velocities over the effective Lagrangian location range, the variations of velocity ahead of the shock front with the dimensionless time t/t_{end} for different constant impact velocities are obtained, as shown in Fig. 6, in which t_{end} is the end time corresponding to the time when the shock front reaches the supporting end. It is found that the velocity ahead of the shock front is roughly independent of the constant-impact velocity and keeps at a level with some fluctuation, which may be due to the interaction of the elastic wave of the cell walls ahead of the shock front. Fig. 6 also indicates that the velocity at the initial and the terminal stages is relatively low, when the shock front locates within one cell size from one end of the specimen. That is due to the boundary effect. Thus, the velocities at these two stages are not used to calculate the average value of the velocity ahead of the shock front. The particle velocity ahead of the shock front, V_A , is then obtained, as schematically illustrated in Fig. 6.

3.3 The effect of relative density on the shock wave speed

The cell-based finite element models with varying relative densities are simulated to study the dependence of shock wave speed on the relative density. In the above section, the particle velocity

ahead of the shock front has been discussed and it should be taken into consideration under constant-velocity impact. According to Eq. (11), the constant term c in a certain relative density could be determined from the data of shock wave speed and the corresponding velocity jump across the shock front. Then, the influence of the relative densities on the material parameter c could be investigated using a range of densities, as shown in Fig. 7. The results exhibit a nearly linear tendency and a linear fitting expression is estimated as

$$c = 23.2(1 + 5.40\rho) \text{ m/s} . \quad (12)$$

Figure 7: Variation of material parameter c with relative density.

It claims that the relative density is one of the most important variables influencing the properties of shock wave propagation in cellular materials. For a fixed constant-velocity impact, the shock wave speed increases linearly with the relative density of cellular materials. With the increase of the relative density, the cell-wall thickness becomes much thick and the compressible volume becomes small in cellular materials with negligible lateral expansion [21]. Thus, the shock front propagates much quicker as the cellular materials with a high relative density need a longer compacted region behind the shock front to reach the same loading displacement than that with a low relative density.

3.4 Comparison with the R-PH model

The expression of the shock wave speed with respect to the velocity jump across the shock front and the relative density is obtained by using the velocity field method. According to Eq. (12), the strain hardening parameter D of cellular material under dynamic loading could be expressed as

$$D = c^2 \rho_0 = 1.45\rho(1 + 5.40\rho)^2 \text{ MPa} . \quad (13)$$

Under quasi-static loading, the strain hardening parameter C has already determined in Section 2.2 by fitting the quasi-static nominal stress-strain curve using the R-PH idealization. A comparison between the two strain hardening parameters D and C as a function of the relative density is shown in Fig. 8. The strain hardening parameters increase with the increase of relative density, which could be physically understood as the fact that the increasing relative density may increase the flexure strength of the cell walls that increases the strain hardening parameter in cellular materials. For a given relative

density, the strain hardening parameter under quasi-static loading is larger than that under dynamic impact, which is related to the difference of deformation mechanisms under different loading rates [9]. Under dynamic crushing, the cells behind shock front are much tightly stacked and could reach a higher strain compared with the quasi-static behavior. Hence, the R-PH idealization model underestimates the dynamic response of cellular materials in the densification stage under high enough impact loading. So the D-R-PH shock model is an improvement on the R-PH shock model for cellular materials under dynamic impact.

Figure 8: Comparison of the strain hardening parameter under quasi-static and dynamic loading.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The cell-based finite element model is generated to investigate the effect of relative density on the shock wave speed of cellular materials under constant-velocity compression. Local velocity fields are calculated to characterize the propagation feature of shock wave in cellular materials. It provides the fact that there exists a nearly planar shock front propagating through cellular materials under high constant-velocity compression.

The shock wave speed is determined based on the velocity distribution along the impact direction. It shows that the shock wave speed has a linear relation with the impact velocity at a specific relative density of cellular material. However, the velocity ahead of shock front is not in a stationary state and it should not be neglected under constant-velocity impact. So it is appropriate to revise the impact velocity to the velocity jump across the shock front in the relation of the shock wave speed. The result indicates that the shock wave speed increases linearly with the relative density.

The influence of relative density on the strain hardening parameter is investigated and analyzed. The result shows that the strain hardening parameter increases with the relative density. For a specific density, the strain hardening parameter of quasi-static loading is higher than that of dynamic impact.

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